

Synthesis of 2-Methyl 6-Ethyl and 2-Methyl 6-n-Propyl- γ -pyrones.

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By treating triacetic acid lactone (I) with propionic and *n*-butyric anhydrides in presence of sulphuric acid the 5-propionyl and 5-*n*-butyryl products of (I) are prepared. By boiling with hydrochloric acid these are converted into the hydrochlorides of 2-methyl 6-ethyl and 2-methyl 6-*n*-propyl- γ -pyrones respectively. The pyrones and their derivatives are described. The corresponding pyridones prepared from them are described. The action of acetic butyric anhydride on (I) is also described.

DEACETYLATION of dehydracetic acid (II) (2-methyl 5 acetyl 4 : 6 diketo 5 : 6 dihydro γ pyran) by heating with 90% sulphuric acid affords¹ the triacetic acid lactone (I). The latter on heating with acetic anhydride-sulphuric acid regenerates (II)²

We were interested to see whether reaction (2) could be a general *c*-acylation reaction of (I) effected with other anhydrides. *C*-acylations of this kind were effected with acetone dicarboxylic acid by one of us³. The *C*-acylation product (III) to be formed would give on boiling with hydrochloric acid the hydrochloride of the pyrone (V), and would thus provide a method for the synthesis of 2 : 6 unsymmetrically substituted γ pyrones.

Treatment of (I) with propionic anhydride and *n*-butyric anhydride furnished (III)a and (III)b respectively in good yields.

In experiments on *C*-acylation of acetone dicarboxylic acid³ with these anhydrides it was found that

butyric anhydride in comparison with acetic anhydride was a poor *C*-acylating agent. But with respect to *C*-acylation of (I) it was found surprisingly as effective as if not more than-acetic anhydride. Imido derivatives (IV)a and (IV)b were prepared for characterisation of (III)a and (III)b respectively according to published procedure⁴.

On refluxing with strong hydrochloric acid (III)a and (III)b gave the hydrochlorides of the pyrones (V)a

and (V)b respectively from which the pyrones were generated. These are characterised by their analytical data and by preparation and analysis of their derivatives (i) the hydrochlorides (ii) chloroplatinates (iii) picrates. Heated with ammonia in a sealed tube the corresponding pyridones (VI)a and (VI)b were obtained. These are characterised by their physical constants and analytical data.

The pyrone structures (V)a and (V)b are supported by their I.R. absorptions which with respect to important peaks are almost the same as of 2:6 dimethyl γ pyrone (V) (R = CH₃) the standard pyrone. Table 1 furnishes the spectral data and Table 2 shows the physical constant of the pyrones(V)a and (V)b and of their derivatives.

Triacetic acid lactone : This was prepared from (II) as per Collie's¹ conditions and after trial experiments for increase of yield. (II) 20 g. was dissolved in 90% sulphuric acid, and the solution was heated in oilbath at 130°. If the acid is slightly weak, (II) isomerises to isodehydracetic acid. If it is stronger than 90% there is charring. 130° is the optimum temperature. If it is few degrees less no conversion takes place. The heating is continued till a drop of the liquid poured in 5 ml. of water fails to produce a precipitate. The contents are then quickly poured over 50 g. of crushed ice. The lactone crystallises out at once. Yield of the crude product 15 g. It crystallises from water in colourless needles melting at 187°.

TABLE 1— I.A. ABSORPTIONS OF THE PYRONES

(V) 2:6 dimethyl- γ -pyrone										
Wave lengths in microns	3.4	3.49	6.02	6.25	6.94	7.18	7.27	8.61	10.81	11.11
Wave numbers Cm ⁻¹	2930	2860	1660	1600	1440	1392	1375	1150	925	900
	S	M	V.S.	V.S.	M	V.S.	S	M	M	S
(V)a. 2-methyl 6-ethyl- γ -pyrone										
Wave lengths in microns	3.36		6.02	6.25	7.01	7.18		8.69	10.91	11.62
Wave numbers Cm ⁻¹	2975		1660	1600	1425	1392		1150	916	860
	W		V.S.	V.S.	M	V.S.		M	M	M
(V)b. 2-methyl 6-n-propyl- γ -pyrone										
Wave lengths in microns	3.38	3.49	6.02	6.15	6.94	7.14	7.48	8.69	10.81	11.62
Wave numbers Cm ⁻¹	2950	2860	1660	1625	1440	400	1350	1150	925	860
	W	M	V.S.	S	M	V.S.	M	M	S	M

TABLE 2— PHYSICAL CONSTANTS OF THE PYRONES AND OF THEIR DERIVATIVES

Acylation products (III)	Imido derivatives (IV)	The pyrones (V)	Derivatives of (V)*			Pyridones (VI)
			hydro chlorides (V)a	chloro platinates (V)a	picrates (V)a	
(III)a m.p. 94°	(IV)a m.p. 130°	(V)a b.p. 150°/18 m.m. m.p. 24°	hydro chlorides (V)a m.p. 104°	chloro platinates (V)a m.p. 182°	picrates (V)a m.p. 55°	(VI)a m.p. 65°
(III)b m.p. 52°	(IV)b m.p. 124°	(V)b b.p. 128°/12 m.m. m.p. 12°	(V)b m.p. 33° hyroscopic	(V)b m.p. 175°	(V)b m.p. 48°	(VI)b m.p. 63°

Action of aceticbutyric anhydride on (I): By treating (I) with aceticbutyric anhydride under conditions described in the experimental part, two products were isolated. The one which after crystallisation melted at 107° was identified as dehydracetic acid (II). The other which after crystallisation melted at 52° was identified as (III)b. The yield of (III)b was appreciably greater than that of (II).

Experimental

Dehydracetic acid (II) : This was prepared by heating acetoacetic ester under reflux and removing alcohol as vapour⁵. Crystallised from 90% alcohol it melts at 108°. It gives acid reaction and on fusion with ammonium acetate gives the imido derivative melting at 198°-200°.

The acylation products (III) : *Lactone of α -propionyl triacetic acid (III) a* : To 9 g. of (I) kept in a small r. b. flask fitted with air condenser were added 27 g. of propionic anhydride (b. p. 165°-170°) followed by 1 ml. of strong sulphuric acid. (I) partly dissolved. After heating on boiling water bath for 40 min. the clear brown solution was poured into excess of ice cold water. The reaction product separated as a dirty white solid which after filtration under suction, crystallised from dilute alcohol in voluminous fine needles melting at 94°. Found C=58.6, H=5.6, C₉H₁₀O₄ requires C=59.2, H=5.6 per cent.

It is sparingly soluble in water and gives acid reaction like (II). Yield of the crude product 9.5 g.

*Did not give any derivative with *p*-nitro phenyl hydrazine.

Lactone of α -n-butyryl triacetic acid (III)b : This was prepared from (I) 20 g, n-butyric anhydride (b.p. 188°-190°) 50 g. and strong sulphuric acid 1.5 ml. in the same manner as in (III)a. Yield of the crude product 18 g. A further crop of 4 g. was deposited from mother liquor on standing. It crystallises from warm aqueous alcohol in colourless thin plates melting at 52° and resembles (II) and (III)a in being sparingly soluble in water and giving acid reaction. Found C=61.1, H=6.1, C₁₀H₁₂O₄ requires C=61.2, H=6.1 per cent.

The imido derivatives (IV). (IV)a : A mixture of 0.25 g of (III)a and 1.25 g. of ammonium acetate kept in a small tube was gently heated to fusion over a small flame for 5 min. On cooling adding water and rubbing the imido compound separated as a solid which crystallised from water in small needles melting at 130°. (IV)b similarly prepared and crystallised, melts at 124°

The pyrones (V). 2-methyl 6-ethyl- γ -pyrone (V)a : To 25 g. of (III)_a kept in 500 ml. r. b. flask fitted with air condenser, 200 ml. of hydrochloric acid (Sp. gr. 1.16) was added and the contents were gently heated over a small flame. Gradually a clear brown solution was formed. The heating was continued for 3 hrs and after that for another 40 min. The excess of acid was removed by distillation under reduced pressure till about 40 ml. of the liquid remained consisting of the hydrochloride dissolved in hydrochloric acid. On adding to the cooled solution caustic soda in slight excess, extracting the liberated pyrone repeatedly with ether, washing with a little water, drying and distilling off the solvent, the remaining pyrone was distilled at reduced pressure. It was collected as a thin liquid at 150° 15 m.m. yield 10 g. Found C=70.0, H=7.8. C₈H₁₀O₂ requires C=69.5, H=7.2 per cent.

The pyrone is a thin pale yellow liquid which on cooling in ice-chest crystallised out in almost colourless long needles melting at 24°. It is very soluble in water.

The hydrochloride : The pyrone 0.4 ml. was dissolved in equal volume of water. 3 ml. of 20% hydrochloric acid was added and the solution transferred to a watch glass. On standing over night the hydrochloride separated in white thin plates which on drying over porous plate melted at 104°. Found HCl=20.1, C₈H₁₀O₂ requires HCl=20.9 per cent.

The chloroplatinate : To the solution of the pyrone in strong hydrochloric acid was added a solution of chloroplatinic acid in the same solvent. On rubbing with glass rod and allowing to stand the chloroplatinate separated in big orange crystals, which on washing and drying on porous plate melted at 182° (decomp). Found Pt=27.7, (C₈H₁₀O₂)₂ H₂ Pt Cl₆ requires Pt=28.4 per cent.

The picrate : A saturated aqueous solution of picric acid was added to a concentrated aqueous solution of the pyrone till it became turbid. A drop of hydrochloric acid was added and the solution was left in ice-chest for a few hours. The picrate slowly crystallised

out in long yellow needles melting at 55°. Found picric acid=62.3, C₈H₁₀O₂, C₆H₂(NO₂)₃OH requires picric acid 62.4 per cent.

2-methyl 6-n-propyl pyrone γ (V)b : The pyrone was prepared from (III)b in the same manner as (V)a. 20 g. of (III)b gave 9 g. of the liquid pyrone b.p. 128°/2 mm. Found C=71.2, H=7.9, C₉H₁₂O₂ requires C=71.05, H=7.9 per cent.

It is a thin liquid, less soluble in water than (V)a. On standing in ice-chest it crystallised out in colourless long needles melting at 12°.

The hydrochloride : Attempts to prepare the hydrochloride in the usual way resulted in the formation of a thick syrup which could not be induced to crystallise. When left in contact with dry ether in a tube in ice-chest over-night the hydrochloride separated in needles, which after filtering off the ether and drying at 0° on porous plate melted at 33°. Found HCl=20.5, C₉H₁₂O₂, requires HCl=19.3 per cent.

The chloroplatinate : Prepared as in the case of the lower homologue melted at 175°. Found Pt=27.6, (C₉H₁₂O₂)₂ H₂ Pt Cl₆ requires Pt=27.8 per cent.

The picrate : Prepared as usual melted at 48°. Found picric acid=62.3 C₉H₁₂O₂, C₆H₂(NO₂)₃OH requires picric acid 62.4 per cent.

The pyridones (VI). 2-methyl 6-ethyl- γ -pyridone (VI)a : A mixture of (V)a 1.5 ml., and liquor ammonia 4.5 ml. was heated in a sealed tube in air oven at 130° for 4 hrs. On cooling and opening the seal the contents were evaporated on a watch glass over boiling water bath. From the resulting thick syrup kept for a few hours in an ice-chest the pyridone separated as a thick cake, which was filtered, dried and crystallised from water in needles melting at 65°. Found C=61.3, H=8.2, N=9.3 C₈H₁₁ON, H₂O* requires C=61.9, H=8.3 N=8.9 per cent. The pyridone is quite soluble in water.

2-methyl 6-n-propyl- γ pyridone (VI) b : This was prepared from (V)b as above. It melts at 63° and like the lower homologue is quite soluble in water. Found C=62.7, H=8.7, N=8.5; C₉H₁₃ON, H₂O* requires C=63.9, H=8.8 N=8.3 per cent.

Action of aceticbutyric anhydride on (I) : 2g. of (I) and 6 g. of the unsymmetrical anhydride were made to react as in the preparation of (III)a. On pouring the reaction product on crushed ice neither a solid nor an oil separated, but on standing in ice-chest a small amount of a solid slowly deposited. The latter after filtration and crystallisation melted at 107° and was identified as (II) (mixed melting point with (II) 107°) On repeated extraction of the filtrate with ether, washing, drying and distilling off the solvent a dark oil remained which when left in contact with crushed ice solidified. The solid after crystallisation melted at 52° and was identified as (III)b (mixed m.p. 52°)

*2:6 diethyl and 2:6 di-n-propyl γ -pyridones are also monohydrates. Ref. 3

From the weights of the two components which could be isolated in crude form from the solution it is calculated that the total reaction of (I) was 65% of theoretical, comprising of 15% in acetylation and 50% in butyrylation.

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